

THE EVALUATION OF THE PARTICIPATION OF GAME AND PHYSICAL EDUCATION LESSON OF THE MILD SEVERE DEGREE MENTAL RETARDATION AND AUTISTIC STUDENTS

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Abstract:

The aim of this research is to evaluate the acquisition of mild degree mentally disabled students; severe degree mentally disabled students and autistic students in game and physical activities and physical education lessons. The research was done to describe current situation. Nineteen special education teachers and one physical education teacher joined the research voluntarily. Teacher's evaluated 44 mild degrees mentally disabled students, 31 severe mentally disabled students and 10 autistic students with the evaluation form of game and physical activities. Descriptive statistic techniques were used during the data analysis. According to research result, 1st-2nd-3rd class mild degree mentally disabled students, gallop skill should be developed and also severe degree mentally disabled one in mild level. It was seen that students one in sufficient level. Teachers gave the idea that 4th grade mentally disabled students should the skill of kicking the ball with a racked, folk dances, creative / cultural dances, designing a game, developing a programme and preparing a demonstration they are evaluated as middle and good in jumping, taking step and jumping and joining the game. But in other skills, they are evaluated as good and very good. It is resulted that 4th grade severe degree mentally disabled students are good and very good in running, jumping, hitting, throwing and catching skills; creative/cultural designing a game, developing programmes, preparing a demonstration should be developed. As a result, in the movements that were requiring object control, creative, cultural dances, designing a game, developing a program, preparing a demonstration, joining game skills should be developed.

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1. Introduction

A well planned, regular, and free physical education and exercise, social, and cultural programs have positive physical and mental effects on disabled persons (Gürer et al., 2014; Kılınç et al., 2015; Şahin et al., 2014; Winnick and Nad, 1985; Winnick, 1990; Yılmaz et al., 2015; Alıncak et al., 2016a; Alıncak and Uğurlu, 2016; Alıncak et al., 2016b; Öztürk and Abakay, 2014), besides exercise has same effects on healthy persons (Biçer and Akkuş, 2005; Dedecan et al., 2016; Akcan and Biçer, 2015; Özdal, 2016a; Biçer et al., 2015; Özdal, 2016b; Özdal, 2015). In addition to psychological effects, it is removable that physical activity is factor that effect physical and rehabilitation, period of disabled people (Gür, 2011).

Jannsen and Le Blanc (2010) advice in their studies that children and the young that between 5 and 17 should join a moderate level physical activity at least 1 hour in a day. In İlhan (2009)'s study 95% percent of parents want their mentally disabled children to joining the physical education and sports activity in special education programme.

In Ayan et al., (2012), it was found that children, who needed special education, should passive approaches to games and toys. But, when the time went on with the help of the correct inspiration, nearly they preferred like a normal developing child both in game duties and toy preference.

Mental retardation is described as mental functions under the normal level. In other words, it is seen that children have two or more irritability in communication, self-care, family life, social skills, academic functions directing her / him, health and security, free time, learning a job and adaptive behaviors.

Autism: American Psychiatric Association describes that autism is a developmental disturbance which is character mentally disabled as irritability in social interest interaction; verbal and non-verbal communication disturbance; repeated behaviors and lock of interest (Girli and Atasoy, 2010).

Special education is a total of educational services of which goal are to release the possibility of living freely of the person (Canöz, 2011).

A person who needs special education: It is a person who shows more meaningful difference than expected in them of personal quality and education proficiency (Canöz, 2011).

Special education institution: Special education application that is presented to people who needs special requirement in Turkey is conducted at preschool and primary

school, vocational school, vocation education centres, general education schools as main streaming education, special class supportive education rooms, special education and rehabilitation centres.

Generally, mild and severe degree mentally disabled students go attend special education application centres. The children have not been able to follow the applied programmes in primary school. It is aimed that students should develop their self-care daily life skills, functional academic skills and provides harmony to the society. Special class application is composed of classes within pre-school, primary school and secondary school where main streaming students are educating (MEB, 2012).

Classification of mentally disabled students in terms of education: In literature, many mentally disabled students have been classified. According to the aim of the study, some methods below one used in terms of educational and intelligence point. It is divided in to three groups as educable (low degree mentally disabled person), teachable (middle level mentally disabled person) and severe degree mentally disabled (Özokçu, 2013).

Classifying according to the intelligence test point:

- Low level mental disability: 50 / 70.
- Middle level mental disability: 35 / 55.
- Severe level mental disability: 20 / 40.
- More severe level mental disability: Below 20 (Eripek, 2003).

Game and physical activities course is applied to the MEB's 1st, second, third and fourth grade students (disabled or not). The aim of game and physical activities course is to develop the students life skills with basic movements, active and healthy life skills, concepts and strategies and prepare then to latter education grade (MEB, 2012).

Children become social with games. They learn participating and getting in to a group. They reveal their real emotions and thoughts with game. They reflect their inner life. They know their world and check (Yavuzer, 1993).

Sport is canalized mentally disabled a person to social life. The emotion belonging to a group develops with the students who do sports. The disabled person who do any sport away its disability and reveals its unknown identity and skills (Groff et al., 2009). Peoples fixed movements decrease and social development increase when they do physical activity (Orsmond et al., 2004).

When the benefits of mentally disabled peoples participation to the physical activity is evaluated in terms of philosophy, it is emphasized that mentally disabled and these activities have positive effects on developing affective and psychomotor skill (Özer, 2013). Children with down syndrome has more wounding risk because they have

low muscle mass, excessively moving articulation and poor muscle and pigments (Krebs, 2005).

2. Material and Method

2.1. Research Group

This research was planned according to descriptive model with the participation of 6 special education class (44 students), 1 education–application school (31 students) and 1 autistic children education center (10 students), 19 special education teacher and 1 physical education teacher (from autistic children education center) and it was achieved to the population. Student’s disability situation, number of teachers and number of the students in classes is given below.

Table 1: Disability Situation and Number of Students According to Grades

Disability Situation	Grade	Number of Teachers	Number of Students	Total
Mild mentally disabled	1.2.3. grade	Special education class teacher	22	44
	4. grade	Special education class teacher	22	
Severe mentally disabled	1.2.3. grade	Special education class teacher	19	31
	4. grade	Special education class teacher	12	
Autistic students	1.2.3. grade	Physical education teacher	7	10
	4. grade		3	

2.2 Data Collecting Tools

Game and physical activities evaluation form was the one which is proponed by Turkish Republic Ministry of Education, General management of basic education, was used to collect data (Meb, 2012).

2.3 Collecting Data

The list of the schools who has special education classes, education applying schools and autistic children education centres were look from Kirikkale Guidance and Research Center. Researcher went to the special education classes, education applying school and autistic children education center. Necessary explanation was given to the volunteer primary teacher about game and physical activities evaluation form.

2.4 Data Analysis

Data frequency and percentage was taken with using SPSS 22.0 packet statistic program.

3. Results

Game and physical activities course evaluation of how degree mentally disabled, severe degree mentally disabled and autistic children is given with tables and comments in this part. 1st, 2nd,3rd grade low degree mentally disabled students game and physical activities course evaluation is given of Table 2.

Table 2: 1st, 2nd,3rd grade, low level mentally disabled students game and physical activities course evaluation

1 st , 2 nd ,3 rd grade (n=22)	Should be developed		Adequate/Enough	
	f	%	%	f
Walking			22	100
Running			22	100
Rolling	2	9.1	20	90.9
Jumping	3	13.6	19	86.4
Sliding	4	18.2	18	81.8
Hopping	4	18.2	18	81.8
Hiking	4	18.2	18	81.8
Galloping	12	54.5	10	45.5

In 1st, 2nd, 3rd grade mentally disabled students game and physical activities course, walking 86.4% (45.5% good , 40.9% very good), running 73.3% (36.4% good, 40.9% very good) , Jumping 77.3% (36.4% good, 40.9% very good) , taking step and hopping 63.6% (31.8% good, %31.8 very good) were signed as good and very good by teachers. Galop (54.5%) achieved the result of the development of the skill. It was evaluated that galloping should have been developed. The evaluation of 1-2-3 classes about of the game and physical activities course of mentally disabled students at the heavy level of the class is given in Table 3.

Table 3: 1st, 2nd, 3rd grade severe degree mentally disabled student's game and physical activities course evaluation of 1st, 2nd, 3rd grade severe degree mentally disabled students game and physical activities course

1 st , 2 nd , 3 rd grade (n=19)	Should be developed		Adequate	
	f	%	f	%
Walking	2	10.5	17	89.5
Running	2	10.5	17	89.5
Sliding	3	15.8	16	84.2
Jumping	4	21.1	15	78.9
Hiking	4	21.1	15	78.9
Rolling	4	21.1	15	78.9
Taking step/hopping	5	26.3	14	73.7
Galloping	6	31.6	13	68.4

It was founded that severe degree mentally disabled students should be developed in galloping skill 73.7% (should be developed 31.6%, medium level 42.1%) and they are in medium level. Very good choice was signed at the percentage of 47.4% for jumping and rolling skills. Walking skill (89.5%) running skill (63.2%) were evaluated as very good. Taking steps / hopping and sliding skills were signed as good (52.6%). It was seen that very good choice isn't signed for any students in taking steps/ hopping and galloping skills. The evaluation of 1-2-3 classes' autistic students about of the game and physical activities course is given in Table 4.

Table 4: 1-2-3 class game and physical activities assessment of class autistic students

1 st , 2 nd , 3 rd grade (n=7)	Should be developed		Adequate	
	f	%	f	%
Walking	1	14.3	6	85.7
Running	1	14.3	6	85.7
Jumping	2	28.6	5	71.4
Taking steps/hopping	1	14.3	6	85.7
Galloping	1	14.3	6	85.7
Sliding	1	14.3	6	85.7
Rolling	1	14.3	6	85.7
Hiking	1	14.3	6	85.7

Galloping, sliding, rolling, hiking skills were evaluated as 57.1% good at 1./2./3. grade autistic student's game and physical activities course. Good choice was signed at the percentage of 71.4% for taking steps / hopping skill. Jumping (good 42.9%, very good 28.2%) running (28.6% good, 42.9% very good) skills were founded at good and very good degree.

Table 5: 4th grade low degree mentally disabled student's game and physical activities course evaluation

4. grade (n=22) low grade mentally disabled	Should be developed		Middle		Good		Very Good	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Running	1	4.5	4	18.2	9	40.9	8	36.4
Jumping	2	9.1	7	31.8	5	22.7	8	36.4
Taking steps / hopping	3	13.6	7	31.8	5	22.7	7	31.8
Gallopıng	9	40.9	6	27.3	1	4.5	6	27.3
Sliding	4	18.2	9	40.9	2	9.1	7	31.8
Stretching	3	13.6	7	31.8	8	36.4	4	18.2
Balance	2	9.1	4	18.2	9	40.9	7	31.8
Jumping/Landing	3	13.6	7	31.8	6	27.3	6	27.3
Pushing	2	9.1	4	18.2	8	36.4	8	36.4
Pulling	2	9.1	6	27.3	6	27.3	8	36.4
Throwing	1	4.5	6	27.3	9	40.9	6	27.3
Catching	3	13.6	11	50.0	3	13.6	5	22.7
Kicking	2	9.1	7	31.8	6	27.3	7	31.8
Dribbling	5	22.7	9	40.9	6	27.3	2	9.1
Hitting with a racket	16	72.7	4	18.2	1	4.5	1	4.5
Folk dance	14	63.6	4	18.2	1	4.5	3	13.6
Creative/cultural dances	17	77.3	2	9.1			3	13.6
Participating a game	5	22.7	6	27.3	6	27.3	5	22.7
Designing a game	16	72.7	4	18.2			2	9.1
Developing a programme	19	86.4	2	9.1			1	4.5
Participating regularly	7	31.8	6	27.3	6	27.3	3	13.6
Preparing a show	21	95.5			1	4.5		
Participating eagerly	8	36.4	7	31.8	4	18.2	3	13.6

4th grade low mentally disabled students severe found as good and very good in running 77.3% (good 40.9%, very good 36.4%), balance 71.7% (good 40.9%, very good 31.8%), pushing 72.8% (good 36.4%, very good 36.4%) and throwing 68.2% (good 40.9%, very good 27.3%). They were seen as middle and good level in stretching and throwing 68.2% (middle 31.8%, good 36.4%), catching 63.6% (middle 50.0%, good 13.6%), dribbling 68.2% (middle 40.9%, good 27.3%). It was thought that hitting with a racket (72.7%), folk dances (63.6%), creative-cultural dances (77.3%), designing a game (72.7%), developing a programme (86.4%), preparing a show (95.5%) should have been developed.

Table 6: 4th grade severe degree mentally disabled students game and physical activities course evaluation

4 th grade (n=12) severe degree mentally disabled	Should be developed		Middle		Good		Very Good	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Running	1	8.3	2	16.7	2	16.7	7	58.3
Jumping	3	25.0			5	41.7	4	33.3
Taking steps/hopping	6	50.0			2	16.7	4	33.3
Galloping			7	58.3	2	16.7	3	25.0
Sliding	4	33.3			2	16.7	6	50.0
Stretching	6	50.0			2	16.7	4	33.3
Balance	3	25.0	1	8.3	5	41.7	3	25.0
Jumping/landing	3	25.0	3	25.0	2	16.7	4	33.3
Pushing			1	8.3	7	58.3	4	33.3
Pulling	3	25.0	3	25.0	2	16.7	4	33.3
Throwing			1	8.3	4	33.7	7	58.3
Catching	3	25.0			2	16.7	7	58.3
Kicking			4	33.3	5	41.7	3	25.0
Dribbling	3	25.0	4	33.3	2	16.7	3	25.0
Hitting with a racket	6	50.0	2	16.7	3	25.0	1	8.3
Folk dances	6	50.0	3	25.0	2	16.7	1	8.3
Creative-cultural dances	12	100						
Participating the game	6	50.0	3	25.0	3	25.0		
Designing a game	12	100.0						
Developing a programme	12	100.0						
Participating regularly	6	50.0	2	16.7	2	16.7		
Preparing a show	12	100.0					2	16.7
Participating eagerly	6	50.0	2	16.7	1	8.3	3	25.0

4th grade severe degree mentally disabled students are evaluated as very good in running 58.3%, sliding 50%, throwing and catching 58.3% in game and physical activities course.

It is resulted that all the students 100% in creative and cultural dances, designing a game, developing programme and preparing a Show, 50% of the students in folk dances, participating a game, taking step and hopping and stretching skills should be developed.

It is found that pushing skills 91.6%, (58.3% good, 33.3% very good) and throwing skills 91.6% (33.3% good, 58.3% very good) are at good level. Opinions of 4th grade autistic students about of game and physical activities course are given at the Table 7.

Table 7: Evaluation of 4th grade autistic children in game and physical activities course

4 th grade (n=3) severe degree mentally disabled	Should be develop		Middle		Good		Very Good	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Running	1	33.3					2	66.7
Jumping	1	33.3			1	33.3	1	33.3
Taking steps/hopping	1	33.3			1	33.3	1	33.3
Galloping	1	33.3			1	33.3	1	33.3
Sliding	1	33.3			1	33.3	1	33.3
Stretching			2	66.7			1	33.3
Balance	1	33.3	1	33.3			1	33.3
Jumping /landing	1	33.3					2	66.7
Pushing	1	33.3					2	66.7
Pulling	1	33.3					2	66.7
Throwing	1	33.3					2	66.7
Catching					1	33.3	2	66.7
Kicking	1	33.3					2	66.7
Dribbling			1	33.3			2	66.7
Hitting with a racket	1	33.3					2	66.7
Folk dances	2	66.7	1	33.3				
Creative-cultural dances	2	66.7	1	33.3				
Joining a game	1	33.3	1	33.3	1	3.33		
Designing a game	2		1	33.3				
Developing a programme	3	100.0						
Participating regularly	1	33.3	1	33.3			1	33.3
Preparing a show	2	66.7	1	33.3				
Participating eagerly	1	33.3	1	33.3			1	33.3

It is signed that developing programme should be developed of 100%. It is evaluated that folk dances, creative cultural dances, designing a game and preparing show skills should be developed at 60.7% percentage and medium level at 33.3%. Very good choice is signed in jumping /landing, pulling pushing, throwing, catching, kicking dribbling, hitting with a racket skills signed in catching skills again.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

It is resulted that in game and physical activities course 1.2.3. grade low degree mentally disabled students galloping skills (54%) should be developed. This situation may be based on both teachers and students. It may be seen as should be developed according to mentally disabled students hand-eye coordination, body coordination and inefficiency at motor developments Aydın (2011), informed that teachers couldn't

practice game and physical activities course regularly or they did another course. Some of mentally disabled students show similarities as normal children in terms of physical appearance and they also as skillful as normal children. Even mentally disabled children can be successful in many sports branches like other normal children (Güven, 1986).

This idea supports that first, second, third grade low grade mentally disabled, severe degree mentally disabled and autistic students are generally good at physical activities. But, on the contrary of the findings that are informed that mental disability generally affects physical capacity negatively in literature (Sucuoğlu, 2009; Siedentop et al., 1986; Metin and Işıtan, 2011; Senemoğlu, 1994; Yancı 2001; Eripek, 2005; Krebs, 1995; Özsoy et al., 2002; Belgin and Yücel, 2001).

The reason of this situation is based that teachers cannot evaluate students objectively.

It is found that 4th grade low degree mentally disabled student's folk dances, creative and cultural dances, designing a game, developing a programme, and preparing a show skills should be developed combining classes application is done at 1st-4th and 5th-8th grade classes which is opened for mentally disabled or autistic students. But it is mandatory that courses which are needed special skills, religion and moral and foreign language courses are given by brunch teachers. Class teachers attend the courses given by branch teacher (MEB, 2012).

Because of this physical education teacher cannot give game and physical activities course at 1st 2nd 3rd 4th grade in primary school. Because of this, it can be seen that class teachers can be inadequate in creativity, sense of rhythm, solving problem skills folk dances and dances. If physical education teachers give education at game and physical activities course, teacher can affects the course positively.

The study which was done in Kırıkkale can be applied at the some degree disabled students schools in different cities. Evaluation of game and physical activities course can be done with disabled, combining and not disabled students. Disabled and not disabled students can be compared. Some volunteering projects can be started to develop the participation of students to game and physical activities course especially students in education faculty and disabled students. Common studies can be done by both the ministry of youth and sports and the ministry of education to encourage the students and teachers throughout the country.

If game and physical activities course is given by master teachers, it will be more efficient according to the research of special education teachers, instead of evaluating mentally disabled students, it can be reached more objective results with text protocol proponed by masters in MEB. It is found that taking help from parents, using several materials, caring about from of the movement and process of education, training

warming activities and cooling activities are not done by teacher. It is found that they do not give this course one hour every day.

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